

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B366
 Date: 08 May 2008
 Take Off: 13:55:10Z
 Landing: 17:08:39Z
 Flight Time 3h 13

Campaign: EUCAARI

Operating Area: Rostock-Laage – Eindhoven - Oberpfaffenhofen

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight	
3	CCM1	Dawn Quinn	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist 1	Keith Bower	University of Manchester	
5	Flight Manager	Mo Smith	FAAM	
6	CCN / CCM2	Jamie Trembath	FAAM	
7	Cloud Physics	Jim Crawford	FAAM	Y
8	Wet & Dry Neph / PSAP / Filters / CVI	James Bowles	Met Office	Y,y,n,n,
9	SWS	Debbie O'Sullivan	Met Office	Y
10	AMS	Will Morgan	University of Manchester	N
11	2D-S / CAPS / CPI	Dantong Liu	University of Manchester	N
12	PAN / TDLAS / Core Chem	Alan Wooley	FAAM	Y
13	Mission Scientist 2	Claire McConnell	University of Manchester	

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B366
 Date: 08 May 2008
 Project: EUCAARI
 Location: N Germany, Netherlands, Box A

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
131957		Start-Up	-.06 kft	359	53'54.88N,12'17.33E
134549		Video	-.05 kft	359	Start FFC & UFC
135031	135232	Pir 1	-.05 kft	359	Start 330, right
135510		T/O	1.2 kft	359	Rostock-Laage
135742		Event	4.5 kft	359	Zero JW & Nevz
135756		Video	4.7 kft	359	FFC & DFC
140413	140716	Profile 1	4.8 - 2.0 kft	359	5k-2.2k', QNH 1020hPa
140716	142238	Run 1	2.0 - 2.1 kft	359	2.2k'
140851		Waypoint	2.0 kft	359	3 miles before D5
141603		Event	2.0 kft	359	Q1019
142124		Waypoint	2.0 kft	359	D4
142239	142851	Profile 2	2.1 - 7.8 kft	359	2.2k-8k'
142852	143506	Profile 3	7.8 - 2.4 kft	359	8k'-2.5k', Q1018
142949		Video	7.3 kft	359	Change Tapes
143244		Waypoint	4.5 kft	359	D3
143507	143913	Run 2	2.4 kft	359	2.5k', Q1018
143913	144509	Profile 4	2.4 - 7.9 kft	359	2.5k'-8k'
144509	145112	Profile 5	7.9 - 2.4 kft	359	8k'-2.5k'
145113	145339	Profile 6	2.4 - 4.4 kft	359	2.5k'-4.5k', Q1017
145340	151727	Run 3	4.4 - 4.6 kft	359	4.5k'
145608		Waypoint	4.5 kft	359	Change to FL45
150636		Waypoint	4.5 kft	359	D2
151257		Waypoint	4.5 kft	359	D1
151727	151927	Profile 7	4.6 - 2.0 kft	359	4.5k'-2k'
152048	152800	Run 4	2.0 kft	359	G2-F2, 2k'
152931	153559	Run 5	3.3 - 3.4 kft	359	F2-G2, 3.5k'
153813	154403	Run 6	6.5 kft	359	G2-F2
154617	155257	Run 7.1	11.0 kft	359	F2-G2
155036		Event	11.0 kft	359	Heimann cal
155439	155501	Run 7.2	11.0 kft	359	Aborted, clear to climb
161108		Video	27.0 kft	359	End of tapes
170839		Land	1.8 kft	359	Oberpfaffenhofen
171007		ASP	1.8 kft	359	Close
171421		Shutdown	1.8 kft	359	48'04.68N, 11'17.51E

B366 Track 08-MAY-08

1. Pilot 1 Alan Roberts (DFL)
2. Pilot 2 Ian Ramsay-Rae (DFL)
3. CCM Dawn Quinn (DFL)
4. Core Chemistry - (FAAM)
5. Flight Manager - (FAAM)
6. Cloud Physics – (FAAM)
7. SWS – Debbie O’Sullivan (MO)
8. CPI rack – Dantong Liu (Manchester)
9. wet nephelometer/filters – James Bowles (MO)
10. AMS Rack – William Morgan (Manchester)
11. CCN – Jamie Trembath/Steve Cowan (FAAM)
12. Mission Scientist – Hugh Coe (Manchester)
13. Mission Scientist – Megan Northway (Reading)

Other Comments:

T/O Rostock-Laage: 1400Z
Landing OP: 1740Z

Operating Area: northern Germany; Netherlands, Box A close to Cabauw

Sortie Objectives: To survey northern Germany and Netherlands. Pollution forecasts show strong pollution gradients close to the Netherlands and further west, it is hoped to probe these.

Weather. Atlantic low positioned west of Ireland (1004 mbar) is filling and High off Norwegian coast (1023 mbar), extending over most of central Europe. Occluded front over Irish Sea North-South weakening and stationary. Anticyclonic flow northerly in Baltic, slack to easterly over Central Europe and SE over the North Sea. Light winds, expect close to front over UK.

Flight patterns:

1. Given clear skies (no clouds to interfere with direct radiation) prior to take-off perform pirouette on the runway. (360 degree turn, at around 120 degrees per minute).
2. Take off Rostock-Laage at 1400Z (1600 local)
3. Profile descent from 5000’ to MPA at D5 and follow the route:
D5-D4-D3-D2-D1/F2 along SLR at MPA between waypoints. Possible sawtooth profiles along route, locations to be determined during flight
4. Continue SLR at MPA alongside box A south of D1 (2300 ft). Enter box A and conduct a missed approach of EHEH (Eindhoven) airport, ascend to 3500’.
[1 hr, 40 min]
5. Conduct a seven minute SLR along the length of Box A at 3500 ft between F2 and G2, profile through box A and conduct a second seven minute SLR along the F2-G2 line at an altitude as determined from the D-CMET lidar information.
6. Profile ascent through Box A to upper level airway. End of science.
[40 min, T=2 hr 20 min]
7. Transit back to OP.
[1 hr 20 mins, T=3 hr 40 min]

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B366

Date: 08 may 08	Operator: JC	DRS Time:	DAU1 Time:	DAU2 Time:	DAU3 Time:	Aux1 Time:	Aux2 Time:	Page 1 of 1
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
	133900 seadas running B366.dat pcasp vref=7.5v flow 0.7 2dc on 2dp off sid 1 b366-1.srd ffssp recording on																
	135650 T/O Heaters on																
140413																Start p1	
140505	1200		1	5		0	0									FI40	
140611	1200		1	5		0	0									FI30	
140720	700		1	5		0	0									FI20 end p1 start r1.1	
141000	730		1	5		0	0										
141500	615		2	3		0	0										
142000	650		2	3		0	0										
142300	690		2	3		0	0									End r1.1 start sawtooth	
142430	640		2	3		0	0									FI35	
142509	600		2	3		0	0									FI40	
142608	800		2	3		0	0									FI50	
142720	160		2	3		0	0									FI60	
142814	15		2	1		0	0									FI70	
143000	40		2	1		0	0									FI70	
143108	1500		2	5		0	0									FI60	
143214	2000		2	3		0	0									FI50	
143320	1500		2	3		0	0									FI40	
143430	1500		3	5		0	0									FI30	
143512	1100		3	5		0	0									2500ft end sawtooth, start r2	
144000	950		3	5		0	0									End r2 start p4	
	832		3	5		0	0									FI30	
	877		3	5		0	0									FI40	
	933		3	5		0	0									FI50	
	460		4	3		0	0									FI60	
	30		4	1		0	0									FI70	
	40		4	1		0	0									FI80	

PCASP Reference Volts =	FFSSP Reference Volts =	2D2-C End element 1 voltage =	CIP25 End element 1 voltage =	CIP100 End element 1 voltage =
PCASP Flow rate =		2D2-C End element 32 voltage =	CIP25 End element 64 voltage =	CIP100 End element 64 voltage =
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power =	2D2-P End element 1 voltage =		

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B366
Date of flight: 08/05/2008

T/O:
Land:

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		DONE IN EXETER
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B366
Date of Flight: 08/05/2008

B) 2D PROCESSING		REPROCESS +1hr
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC		
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)		
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS		
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) Unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip		Size of Bnnn.dat = 81870
6) FLOODS> WAVE WAVE> CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Blocks read =26049 Blocks written = 26049 Bad reads =0
7) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 5 min)</i> f) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land + 5 min)</i> g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data: Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N		Start = 0 End = 240000 Ignore error message scroll (vestigial error from tapes) Are FRW, FSP, IMB, PCA,SEC files in PMSDATA? Are they non-zero in size? yes
8) FLOODS> WAVE i). WAVE> imagedisplay a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) File generation no: 0 d) Time from IWC plot: N e) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP f) Start time: <i>As in 7e above</i> g) End time: <i>As in 7f above</i> h) Time interval (sec): 5 recommended (0 for all images) ii). WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 1 min)</i> e) Enter end time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 1 min)</i> f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks: 10 iii). WAVE> exit to create files iv). FTP ascii *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC v). Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter vi). Output as pdf file (720 dpi resolution), appending name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files		2D image display and printing Must be done from FLOODS itself. Note any problems with images 2dp almost all noise. Possibly some useful frames near end of flight Prepare imagery for Core data From own PC again Start = End = FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_ Bnnn_2Dx-images.ps Notes on this in instructions

<p>9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_tas g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>		<p>NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful.</p> <p>X =</p> <p>Start = End =</p> <p>Time data processed to =</p> <p>2dproc files present? *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat</p>
<p>10) FLOODS> WAVE</p> <p>i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit</p>		<p>Use PVWAVE for this section</p> <p>Error message about HDDR file should be ignored.</p> <p>Records =31</p>
<p>11) FLOODS> MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>		<p>X = Y = (X+1)</p>
<p>12) CHECKS:</p> <p>Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i></p>	<p>N</p>	<p>Use flight_plot to check data is present in mfd file?</p>

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B
Date of Flight:

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:		
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. (1.15ccs⁻¹ Feb 07)</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Min size =1 Vol flow rate =0.7
3) FLOODS> WAVE i).WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' ii). WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_tas_2d_pcasp d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		X = Y = X+1 =
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and JW peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph – total blue scatter.</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>	N	Is data present in mfd? Use flight_plot to check.

B366_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog.txt

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12:56:16.38 --- - - - -
12:56:16.38 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
12:56:16.38 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
12:56:16.38 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B366
12:56:16.38 --- - - - -
12:56:37.05 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
12:56:47.01 SWS - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
12:56:48.51 USH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
12:56:50.12 LSH - 100 - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
12:56:50.59 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
12:56:50.68 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
12:56:50.77 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
12:56:54.72 SWS - - 40 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
12:56:55.57 SWS - - - 40 - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 40ms.
12:56:57.86 USH - - - 5 - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
12:57:00.15 USH - - 50 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
12:57:00.17 USH - - - 50 - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
12:57:01.98 LSH - - - 5 - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
12:57:04.23 LSH - - 600 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
12:57:04.24 LSH - - - 600 - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
12:57:10.70 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:57:10.71 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:57:10.71 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:57:18.10 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
12:57:21.73 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:57:21.74 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:57:22.22 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:57:22.71 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:57:22.80 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:57:24.66 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:57:24.77 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:57:25.60 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:57:25.71 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:57:28.50 SWS - - - - Idling
12:57:28.51 USH - - - - Idling
12:57:28.73 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:25:31.06 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:25:31.06 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:25:39.28 SWS 0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
13:25:59.21 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 0.000
13:26:03.44 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:26:03.44 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:26:03.68 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:26:03.71 SWS - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:26:03.92 USH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:26:04.33 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:26:04.66 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:26:04.69 LSH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:26:10.11 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
13:26:10.33 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:26:59.05 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
13:27:03.85 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:27:03.87 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:27:04.33 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:27:04.80 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:27:04.94 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:27:10.76 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:27:13.05 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:27:13.09 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:27:13.47 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:27:13.89 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:27:14.22 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:27:19.93 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:30:33.41 --- - - - - *** cooler at 6 deg
13:35:48.21 --- - - - - *** cooler at 7 deg
13:42:22.05 --- - - - - Reset shutters.

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13:42:27.15 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:42:27.17 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:42:27.75 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:42:28.16 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:42:28.25 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:42:34.19 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:42:41.52 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:42:41.59 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:42:41.90 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:42:42.49 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:42:42.67 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:42:48.41 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:50:49.95 --- - - - - *** piroheutte 2 sza 47.84 saa 236.12 temp 6
deg starting on heading 330 turning to right
13:52:33.59 --- - - - - *** end of piroheutte 2
14:00:42.56 SWS - - - - Idling
14:00:42.62 USH - - - - Idling
14:00:42.82 LSH - - - - Idling
14:00:44.77 SWS 0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
14:00:46.63 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:00:46.63 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:00:46.64 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:00:49.20 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
14:00:54.29 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:00:54.31 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:00:54.71 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:00:55.14 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:00:55.44 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:01:01.20 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:01:06.36 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:01:06.44 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:01:06.49 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:01:07.19 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:01:07.75 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:01:13.04 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:01:28.81 --- - - - - *** cooler at 5 deg
14:03:28.74 --- - - - - *** 6 deg
14:04:14.48 --- - - - - *** start of profile descent
14:06:11.74 SWS - - 30 - VIS int.time changed from 40ms to 30ms.
14:06:11.74 SWS - - - 30 NIR int.time changed from 40ms to 30ms.
14:06:15.49 SWS - - - - Idling
14:06:16.88 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:06:17.64 SWS - - - - Idling
14:06:19.35 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:06:20.53 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:06:21.30 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:06:22.87 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:06:23.67 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:06:25.41 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
14:06:32.62 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:06:32.64 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:06:32.83 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:06:33.59 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:06:33.62 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:06:38.31 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:06:38.38 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
14:06:39.28 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:06:39.31 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:06:39.46 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
14:06:51.19 --- - - - - *** cooler at 7 deg
14:07:17.44 --- - - - - *** end of p1 and atrt of run at 2200
14:08:54.49 --- - - - - *** turning just before D5
14:13:04.33 --- - - - - *** cooler at 6 deg
14:21:46.63 --- - - - - ***
14:22:41.47 --- - - - - *** end of run start of climb
14:23:15.57 SWS - - - - Idling
14:23:15.64 USH - - - - Idling
14:23:15.81 LSH - - - - Idling
14:23:19.34 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope sent to 174.000

```

14:23:21.03	SWS	172.3	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:23:23.79	USH		-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:23:23.79	LSH		-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:23:23.80	SWS		-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:23:26.93	---		-	-	-	Reset shutters.
14:23:31.18	USH		-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:23:31.22	SWS		-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:23:31.70	LSH		-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:23:32.16	SWS		-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:23:32.20	USH		-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:23:35.84	SWS		-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:23:35.87	USH		-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:23:36.63	SWS		-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:23:37.05	USH		-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:23:38.21	LSH		-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:23:55.66	SWS		-	-	40	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 40ms.
14:23:55.67	SWS		-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 30ms to 40ms.
14:23:59.41	SWS		-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:24:00.25	SWS		-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:24:02.32	SWS		-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:24:03.22	SWS		-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:24:08.10	SWS		-	-	50	VIS int.time changed from 40ms to 50ms.
14:24:08.11	SWS		-	-	50	NIR int.time changed from 40ms to 50ms.
14:24:11.02	SWS		-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:24:12.04	SWS		-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:24:13.52	SWS		-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:24:14.45	SWS		-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:24:17.13	---		-	-	-	Reset shutters.
14:24:20.93	SWS		-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:24:20.95	USH		-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:24:21.17	LSH		-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:24:21.91	SWS		-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:24:22.10	USH		-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:24:25.70	USH		-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:24:25.75	SWS		-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:24:26.69	USH		-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:24:26.85	SWS		-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:24:27.81	LSH		-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:24:30.58	USH		-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:24:30.63	SWS		-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:24:31.13	LSH		-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:24:31.55	USH		-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:24:31.80	SWS		-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:24:38.21	LSH		-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:27:44.58	---		-	-	-	*** cooler at 5 deg
14:28:55.71	---		-	-	-	*** run 2
14:29:00.78	---		-	-	-	*** at 8000 ft
14:30:07.06	---		-	-	-	*** correctionend of profile 1 and start of
profile 2 at 8000 ft						
14:30:23.85	---		-	-	-	*** correctiononn p2 and p3 not p1 and p2
14:30:31.69	---		-	-	-	*** cooler at 6 deg
14:33:42.92	---		-	-	-	*** cooler at 7 deg
14:35:08.02	---		-	-	-	*** end of profile 3 and start of run at 2500
ft						
14:38:13.49	---		-	-	-	*** cooler at 6 deg
14:39:15.02	---		-	-	-	*** end of run start of profile ascent
(sawtooth)						
14:45:11.17	---		-	-	-	*** end of p4 at 8000 ft start of p5
14:51:15.66	---		-	-	-	*** p
14:51:50.56	---		-	-	-	*** p was the end of profile 5 and start of
profile 6 at 2500 ft						
14:51:55.96	---		-	-	-	*** cooler temp 5 deg
14:53:18.28	---		-	-	-	*** cooler at 6 deg
14:53:41.46	---		-	-	-	*** end of p start of run at 4500ft
14:57:18.89	---		-	-	-	*** cooler at 7 deg
15:03:04.00	SWS		-	-	-	Idling
15:03:04.06	USH		-	-	-	Idling
15:03:04.58	LSH		-	-	-	Idling
15:03:06.96	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000

15:03:08.63	SWS	-4.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:03:10.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:03:10.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:03:10.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:03:16.15	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
15:03:21.22	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:03:21.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:03:21.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:03:22.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:03:22.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:03:28.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:03:30.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:03:30.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:03:30.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:03:31.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:03:31.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:03:36.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:06:38.23	---	-	-	-	-	*** D2
15:12:53.91	---	-	-	-	-	*** D1
15:15:59.98	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler temp 5 deg
15:17:32.05	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run start of p
15:17:38.13	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler temp 6 deg
15:17:47.38	---	-	-	-	-	*** decending to 2000 ft
15:19:23.23	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of profile decent
15:20:49.79	---	-	-	-	-	*** run
15:20:56.43	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 4 started
15:21:31.91	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 7 deg
15:22:07.74	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
15:22:13.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:22:13.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:22:13.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:22:14.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:22:14.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:22:19.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:22:21.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:22:21.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:22:22.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:22:22.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:22:23.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:22:28.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:28:04.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
15:29:32.18	---	-	-	-	-	*** strat of run
15:29:35.29	---	-	-	-	-	*** at 3500ft
15:34:58.27	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
15:35:03.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:35:04.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:35:04.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:35:04.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:35:05.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:35:10.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:35:12.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:35:12.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:35:12.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:35:13.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:35:13.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:35:19.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:36:04.86	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
15:38:09.86	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run 6
15:38:15.95	---	-	-	-	-	*** at 6500 ft
15:39:07.47	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 5 deg
15:42:03.03	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 6 deg
15:44:06.20	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
15:44:46.48	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 7 deg
15:46:18.57	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run 7 at fl 110
15:48:40.53	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
15:48:44.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:48:44.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:48:45.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:48:45.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

15:48:45.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:48:51.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:48:56.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:48:56.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:48:56.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:48:56.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:48:57.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:48:57.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:49:02.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:49:09.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:49:13.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:49:14.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:49:15.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:49:16.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:49:18.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:49:24.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:51:04.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 6 deg
15:53:00.65	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
15:53:35.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:53:35.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:53:35.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:53:38.27	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
15:53:40.01	SWS	173.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:53:41.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:53:41.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:53:41.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:53:45.16	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
15:53:50.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:53:50.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:53:50.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:53:51.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:53:51.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:53:56.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:53:58.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:53:58.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:53:58.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:53:59.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:53:59.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:54:00.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:54:05.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:54:45.12	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run 7.2
15:54:57.14	---	-	-	-	-	*** at 11000 ft recirpocal of last run
15:55:13.33	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run 7.2
15:55:37.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:59:31.95	---	-	-	-	-	*** FL 200
16:02:25.12	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 5 deg
16:03:44.99	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
16:03:50.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:03:50.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:03:50.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:03:50.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:03:51.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:03:51.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:03:55.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:03:56.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:03:59.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:03:59.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:04:00.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:04:00.28	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:04:00.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:04:01.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:04:03.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:04:06.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:04:06.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:04:07.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:04:10.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:04:11.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:04:14.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:04:21.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

16:04:21.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:04:22.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:04:23.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:04:24.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:04:27.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:04:34.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:05:05.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:05:05.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:05:05.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:05:10.18	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
16:05:11.91	SWS	-5.5	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
16:05:14.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:05:14.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:05:14.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:05:20.56	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
16:05:26.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:05:26.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:05:26.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:05:27.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:05:27.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:05:33.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:05:36.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:05:36.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:05:36.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:05:37.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:05:37.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:05:43.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:08:42.58	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 7 deg
16:19:06.67	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 6 deg
16:31:42.49	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
16:31:46.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:31:46.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:31:46.75	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:31:47.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:31:47.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:31:53.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:31:56.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:31:56.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:31:56.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:31:57.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:31:57.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:32:03.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:34:27.45	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 5 deg
16:35:12.97	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 6 deg
16:35:15.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:35:15.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:35:15.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:35:19.55	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
16:35:21.31	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
16:35:24.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:35:24.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:35:24.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:35:26.94	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
16:35:31.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:35:31.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:35:31.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:35:32.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:35:32.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:35:38.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:35:40.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:35:40.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:35:40.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:35:41.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:35:41.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:35:46.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:39:41.08	---	-	-	-	-	*** 7 deg
16:47:21.81	---	-	-	-	-	*** 6 deg
16:54:10.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:54:10.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling

16:54:11.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
16:54:18.39	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
16:54:20.13	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
16:54:24.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:54:24.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:54:24.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:54:28.64	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
16:54:33.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:54:33.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:54:34.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:54:34.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:54:35.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:54:40.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:54:44.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:54:45.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:54:45.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:54:45.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:54:46.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:54:51.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:10:48.44	---	-	-	-	-	*** at 17.01 cooler temp dropped to 5 deg
17:11:36.22	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
17:11:41.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:11:41.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:11:41.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:11:41.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:11:42.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:11:47.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:11:51.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:11:51.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:11:51.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:11:52.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:11:52.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:11:52.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:11:56.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
17:11:56.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling

Flight:

B366

KEY

Not Fitted

Fitted, Not Operated

Duff Data

Minor Problems

OK

Thermometers

Hygrometers

Cameras

Navigation + Aircraft

Misc Core

Radiometers

Cloud Probes

Aerosol

Chemistry

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B366

Date: 08 May 2008

Instruments

1. INU – not run
2. Core Console Aft – outboard keyboard, right-hand rail not operating properly, falling apart?
3. FFC Window – lots of smudges, will require cleaning on return to base.
- 4.

Instrument Status roundup

Neph/PSAP/CVI and Filters - okay

AMS – okay

SMPS – Okay at low level, no good at FL110 and above

CCN - okay

PAN/TDLAS/Core Chem – okay

CAPS/SP2/CPI – CAPS not operated. SP2 okay, even measured high altitude particles

Cloud Physics – 2DP not run, rest okay

SWS – okay

Aircraft

Nil

ISDN Emails

Nil

Satcom-H Calls

Nil

Issues

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B366:

Log	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
De-brief	Sortie De-brief yet to be created by Keith Bower
Mission Scientist log	Log yet to be created by Keith Bower
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
Filters	Awaiting confirmation of whether a log was created from Keith Bower
2D-S / CAPS / CPI	2D-S / CAPS / SP2 / CPI operator does not create a log sheet
AMS log	AMS operator does not create a log sheet
CVI	No log as CVI was only operated on three flights : B376, B377 & B378
PAN	No log available
CCN	CCN operator does not create a log sheet

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	24 Jul 2008	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

2 x Forward Facing Cameras

2 x Upward Facing Cameras

Further digital video recordings in avi format:

faam-video-dfc_faam_20080508_b366_134521_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080508_b366_144521_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080508_b366_154521_1hz.avi

faam-video-rfc_faam_20080508_b366_134517_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080508_b366_144517_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080508_b366_154517_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20080508_b366_134515_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080508_b366_144515_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080508_b366_154515_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20080508_b366_134519_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080508_b366_144519_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080508_b366_154519_1hz.avi

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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